

Integrating Scaffolding Instructional Strategy in Teaching of Cyber Security Fundamentals: Effect on Students' Achievement In Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of the effect of integrating scaffolding instructional strategy on students' achievement in cyber security fundamentals Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 105 students offering cyber security fundamentals. Census sampling technique was used because the population was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was Cyber Security Achievement Test (CSAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three research experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.78 was obtained. A two-week training session was organized within the schools by the researchers for the regular Computer Science Education lecturers. The lecturers for the experimental group used scaffolding instructional strategy while the lecturers for the control group used the lecture method. Mean and standard deviation were used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that students who were taught cyber security fundamentals by integrating scaffolding instructional strategy in the teaching process recorded increased achievement than their counterparts who were taught with the lecture approach. Male students achieved higher than female students taught cyber security fundamentals with a scaffolding instructional strategy. The researchers recommended among others that the University Management should incorporate scaffolding instructional strategies in cyber security education to enhance student achievement.

Keywords: Scaffolding Instructional Strategy, Cyber Security fundamentals, Students' Achievement

Introduction

Cyber security fundamentals are the foundational principles and practices aimed at safeguarding digital systems, networks, and data from cyber threats. This includes understanding the concepts of confidentiality, integrity, and availability, known as the CIA triad, which forms the basis of cyber security (Whitman & Mattord, 2018). The knowledge of risk management strategies, such as identifying vulnerabilities, assessing potential threats, and implementing appropriate controls, is essential. Understanding common cyber threats, such as malware, phishing, and social engineering, is vital for developing effective defense mechanisms (Vacca, 2019).

Furthermore, staying abreast of emerging technologies and evolving cyber threats is crucial for maintaining effective cyber security practices in today's dynamic digital landscape. Cyber security is crucial for protecting sensitive information, personal data, and critical infrastructure from cyber threats, including hacking, data breaches, and malware attacks. It safeguards digital assets, ensures the integrity and confidentiality of information, and helps maintain trust and confidence in online systems and services. Despite the importance of cyber security, students' academic achievement in this field has been consistently poor, reflecting a gap in educational effectiveness. This trend underscores the critical need for innovative teaching methods and educational approaches tailored to the complexities of cyber security concepts and practices. Addressing this challenge requires a concerted effort to enhance teaching strategies and provide students with the necessary support and resources to succeed in this increasingly vital domain. Effective teaching methods play a crucial role in imparting knowledge and skills related to cyber security fundamentals to students.

Teaching methods involve the principles and techniques applied during instruction (Joshua & Olayinka, 2015). They serve as the tools or strategies that educators use to involve their students in meaningful activities, leading to the learning of ideas, values, and facts. Logsdon (2014) described traditional teaching methods as involving teachers demonstrating skills, often on blackboards or overhead projectors; students completing practice work, typically in workbooks or on handouts; teachers reviewing students' work or tests; students taking paper-and-pencil tests; and teachers providing feedback on performance, usually through grades and marking missed items. While these methods may have been effective in the past, today's students seem to require different approaches to become independent and strategic learners (Richa, 2014). As education evolves, there is a shift from traditional teaching methods to non-traditional, student-centered approaches.

The lecture method is a traditional teaching approach where the instructor or lecturer imparts knowledge, information, or ideas to a group of learners. The lecture method is a specific teaching approach that involves the instructor presenting information to students in a predominantly one-way manner, often contrasted with more interactive teaching methods. Marmah (2014), defined lecture as a method whereby one person speaking more or less continuously to a group of people on a particular subject or theme. Lecture method according to them is extremely didactic in approach, teacher-centered, and does not lead to meaningful learning. There are other various teaching methods, and the choice of method(s) often depends on factors such as the subject matter, the age and characteristics of the students, the learning objectives, and the resources available. A study by Ukeh, Okeke, Oliver, Eziokwu, Onovo and Orié (2020), asserted that many students find lecture method to be ineffective in teaching and learning of computer concepts. There is then the need for a trial of the principles of scaffolding instructional strategy.

Scaffolding instructional strategy is an educational approach that involves providing structured support and guidance to learners as they develop new skills or understand complex concepts, gradually withdrawing this support as students become more proficient and independent. Scaffolding is defined as an instructional strategy that a teacher uses to help

learners bridge a cognitive gap or process in their learning to a level they were previously unable to accomplish (Owenbiugie & Iyoha, 2017). Scaffolding is described as guidance or assistance provided by an educator or another individual with expertise, aimed at helping students attain their learning objectives (Jumat & Tasir, 2014). It aims to facilitate learning by breaking down tasks into manageable steps, adjusting the level of assistance based on individual student needs, and promoting active engagement and problem-solving. Scaffolding instructional strategy seems to significantly impact academic achievement by providing guidance to students as well as fostering deeper mastery of complex concepts like cyber security fundamentals.

Academic achievement refers to the measurable outcomes attained by students in their educational pursuits, typically involving their performance in academic tasks, assessments, and examinations. Academic performance is the result of students' mental ability in an educational setting. Jimoh, Idris and Olatunji (2016) viewed academic achievement as the desired success attained by students. Academic achievement according to Ikwuka and Samuel (2017), is referred to as the extent to which a learner, educator, or organisation has met their educational goals, and it is generally assessed by tests or continuous evaluation. Akani (2015) reported that scaffolding is in form of coaching or modeling that supports students as they develop new skills or learn new concept.

A study conducted by Owenbiugie and Iyoha (2017), revealed that scaffolding teaching method was superior to the traditional methods in improving the academic performance of students in financial accounting. A study carried out by Ile and Nwokoeeye (2020), revealed that instructional scaffolding method was superior to the conventional method in improving the achievement of male and female students in financial accounting. Unugo (2021), also revealed that scaffolding teaching strategy improved the achievement of students. In their research examining scaffolding and its effect on students' academic achievement, Azih and Nwosu (2017) as well as Vonna, Mukminatien, and Laksmi (2015) discovered that scaffolding has proven to be an effective teaching method, enhancing students' academic achievements compared to alternative approaches. While the studies mentioned above focused on the effectiveness of the scaffolding instructional strategy in the context of teaching financial accounting, it is important to recognize that cyber security, like financial accounting, is a complex and intricate course that requires a deep understanding and effective teaching methods. Therefore, the findings of these studies may have implications for cyber security as well. The effectiveness of scaffolding instructional strategies in enhancing students' academic achievement in cyber security may reveal gender disparities in performance, with research indicating varied receptivity and outcomes among male and female students.

Gender refers to the social, cultural, and psychological traits typically associated with being male or female. It involves roles, behaviours, and identities that society ascribes to individuals based on their perceived sex. Gender refers to the state of being male or female. Historically, researchers have identified gender as a significant factor influencing a child's academic achievement (Gupta & Sharma, 2012). There has been considerable debate on whether gender truly influences academic achievement, with some researchers asserting that males generally

outperform females in various subjects, while others argue the opposite. However, Unugo (2021), reported that males were better receptors of scaffolding instructional strategy more than their female counterparts. Meanwhile, Owenubiugie and Iyoha (2017) and Ile and Nwokoeye (2020), reported that female performed better than their male counterparts when taught using scaffolding instructional strategy. The issue of gender and its effect on students' academic achievement, particularly in the field of cyber security, remains unresolved. In the study on integrating scaffolding instructional strategies in teaching cyber security fundamentals at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, these contrasting outcomes highlight the need to consider gender differences when evaluating the effectiveness of teaching methods.

Statement of the Problem

The poor academic achievement of computer science education students in Bayelsa State, particularly in the field of cyber security fundamentals, has become a hurdle for educational effectiveness. Despite the increasing importance of cyber security, students frequently struggle to grasp the course's fundamental concepts deeply. Traditional teaching methods have proven inadequate in addressing and bridging this significant knowledge gap. Consequently, students often lack the necessary comprehension and skills required for proficiency in cyber security. This deficiency highlights the urgent need for innovative instructional strategies to enhance students' learning outcomes in this critical field. The integration of scaffolding instructional strategies, which provide structured support to learners, has the potential to enhance student academic achievement. However, there is a lack of empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these strategies in the context of cyber security education. This study filled this gap by investigating the effect of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in cyber security fundamentals in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of integrating scaffolding instructional strategy on students' achievement in cyber security fundamentals Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The study specifically investigated the:

1. effect of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' academic achievement when taught cyber security fundamentals and those taught the same topic using lecture method;
2. influence of gender (male and female) on students' academic achievement when taught cyber security fundamentals using scaffolding instructional strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method?

2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught cyber security fundamentals using scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and scaffolding instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in cyber security fundamentals.

Research Method

Quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. Quasi-experimental research design is characterized by the inability to randomly assign subjects to experimental and control groups (Nworgu, 2015). The population for the study was 105 students (62 experimental group – (38 male and 24 female) and 43 control group) offering cyber security fundamentals. Census sampling technique was used because the population was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was Cyber Security Achievement Test (CSAT) which was developed by the researchers and validated by three research experts. Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-20) formula was used to estimate the reliability of the instrument and a reliability index of 0.78 was obtained.

A two-week training session was organized within the schools by the researchers for the regular Computer Science Education lecturers. The lecturers for the experimental group used scaffolding instructional strategy while the lecturers for the control group used the lecture method. To answer the research questions, mean and standard deviation were used, and the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was applied to test the null hypotheses at alpha level of .50. ANCOVA was chosen because the study used intact classes, and initial differences between groups could not be controlled. The null hypothesis was rejected if the probability value was less than or equal to the significance level of .05 ($P \leq .05$) and not rejected if the probability value was greater ($P > .05$).

Data Analysis and Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (<i>s</i>)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (<i>s</i>)	
Experimental	62	34.68	4.63	38.42	5.11	3.74
Control	43	32.11	4.29	34.95	4.93	2.84
Mean Diff.						.90

Table 1 shows that students taught cyber security fundamentals using the scaffolding instructional strategy (experimental group) had a mean pre-test score of 34.68 with a standard deviation of 4.63 and a mean post-test score of 38.42 with a standard deviation of 5.11, resulting in a mean gain of 3.74. In contrast, students taught using the lecture method (control group) had a mean pre-test score of 32.11 with a standard deviation of 4.29 and a mean post-test score of 34.95 with a standard deviation of 4.93, resulting in a mean gain of 2.84. The mean gain difference between the experimental and control groups is 0.90, indicating that the scaffolding instructional strategy was slightly more effective in improving student achievement.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (<i>s</i>)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (<i>s</i>)	
Male	38	33.89	4.09	36.44	4.85	2.58
Female	24	31.78	3.97	33.86	4.14	2.08
Mean Diff.						.50

The table shows that male students had a higher mean achievement score than female students in both the pre-test and post-test when taught cyber security fundamentals with a scaffolding instructional strategy. Both groups improved their scores from pre-test to post-test, with males showing a mean gain of 2.58 and females a mean gain of 2.08. The mean difference in gains between males and females was 0.50.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught cyber security fundamentals using scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught the same topic using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of students taught cyber security using scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method

Dependent Variable: ACHIEVEMENT

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	92.18	2	46.09	8.56	.00
Intercept	56.11	1	56.11	11.44	.00
GROUP	19.87	1	14.09	9.66	.00
Error	1987.90	103	19.30		
Total	2156.06	105			
Corrected Total	1989.85	104			

Table 3 shows that the calculated F value of 9.66 is significant at .00 which is less than the .05 significant level set for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that a significant difference exists between the mean scores of students taught cyber security fundamentals using scaffolding instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals with scaffolding instructional strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	97.30	2	48.65	6.52	.00	Rejected
Intercept	37.45	1	37.45	5.19	.00	
Pretest	33.81	1	33.81			
Gender	60.71	1	60.71	7.09	.00	
Error	1104.60	60	18.41	10.05	.01	
Total	1333.87	62				
Corrected Total	1256.01	61				

Table 4 shows that the calculated F value is 7.09 which is found to be significant at .00. Since this significant level (.00) is less than the .05 significant level set for the study, the null hypothesis is, accordingly, rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female students taught cyber security fundamentals using scaffolding instructional strategy.

Ho3: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and scaffolding instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in cyber security fundamentals.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the interaction effect of gender and method (scaffolding instructional strategy) on students' achievement in cyber security fundamentals

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
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Corrected Model	78.90	2	39.45	6.91	.00	
Intercept	67.37	1	67.37	5.41	.00	
Methods*Gender	69.11	1	69.11	14.73	.01	Rejected
Error	2200.08	103	21.36			
Total	2415.46	105				
Corrected Total	2018.09	104				

Table 5 shows that the calculated F value is 14.73 which is found to be significant at .01. Since this significant level (.01) is less than the .05 significant level set for the study, the null hypothesis is, accordingly, rejected. This means that there is a significant interaction effect between methods and gender in students' academic achievement scores.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings demonstrated that students who were taught cyber security fundamentals through the scaffolding instructional strategy achieved significantly higher academic achievement compared to those who were taught using the lecture method. This suggests that the scaffolding approach, which provides structured support and gradually reduces assistance as students become more proficient, is more effective in enhancing student academic achievement of cyber security fundamentals. The finding concurs with Owenvbiugie and Iyoha (2017) as well as Unugo (2021), both of whom argued that students taught using scaffolding instructional strategies outperform those taught using traditional lecture methods. These studies highlight the effectiveness of scaffolding in enhancing student understanding and retention of material. Consequently, the use of scaffolding techniques can lead to improved academic performance compared to conventional teaching approaches.

The findings of the study revealed that male students demonstrated higher academic achievement than their female counterparts when taught cyber security fundamentals using a scaffolding instructional strategy. This suggests that the scaffolding approach may have had a differential impact on students based on gender. The finding aligns with Unugo (2021), who asserted that male students are more receptive to scaffolding instructional strategies, indicating they benefit more from this approach. However, this result contrasts with the studies of Owenubiugie and Iyoha (2017) and Ile and Nwokoeye (2020), which independently found that female students outperformed male students in financial accounting when taught using scaffolding methods. These differing outcomes suggest that the effectiveness of scaffolding instructional strategies may vary based on subject matter or other contextual factors.

Conclusion

The study concluded that incorporating scaffolding instructional strategies in teaching cyber security fundamentals significantly enhances student achievement compared to traditional lecture methods. Additionally, male students outperformed female students when taught using the scaffolding approach. These findings suggest that instructional design plays a crucial role in

educational outcomes. Future research should explore tailored strategies to bridge the gender achievement gap in cyber security education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. University Management should incorporate scaffolding instructional strategies in cyber security education to enhance student achievement.
2. Universities stakeholders should encourage a shift from traditional lecture-based teaching to more interactive, scaffolded approaches for better student academic achievement in cyber security courses.

References

- Akani, O. (2015). Impact of instructional scaffolding on students' achievement in Chemistry in secondary schools in Ebonyi State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development*, 3(7), 74-83.
- Ikwuka, O. I. & Samuel, N. N. C. (2017). Effect of computer animation on chemistry academic achievement of secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies (JETERAPS)* 8(2), 98-102.
- Ile, C. M. & Nwokoeye, N. (2020). Effect of scaffolding teaching method on students' academic performance in financial accounting in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 3(1), 150-160.
- Jimoh, A. G., Idris, K. & Olatunji, R. I. (2016). Effect of cooperative learning method on academic achievement of cost accounting students in colleges of education in Ogun state. *International Journal of Educational Development* 6(2), 102-100.
- Joshua, S. M. & Olayinka, T. O. (2015). Perceived influence of cutting-edge teaching/learning methodologies on the acquisition of 21st century business education skills in Nigerian universities. *Association of Business Educators of Nigeria Conference Proceedings*, 2(1), 27-39.
- Jumaat, N. F. & Tashir, Z. (2014). Instructional scaffolding in online learning environment: A MetaAnalysis. *International Conference on Teaching and Learning in Computing and Engineering*, 74-77. <https://doi.10.1109/LaTicE.2014.22>
- Logsdon, A. (2014). Top 4 facts on differentiated instruction vs. traditional methods. Available http://learningdisabilities.about.com/od/instructionalmaterials/tp/differinst_ruct.htm
- Nworgu, B. G. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology (Third Edition)*. Nsukka, Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- Owenvbiugie, R. O. & Iyoha, D. O. (2017). Effect of instructional scaffolding on academic performance of students in financial accounting in secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education Research and Behavioral Sciences*, 6(2), 021-028.
- Richa, L. (2014). Instructional strategies: Find the best approach to encourage independent learning. From http://www.udemy.com/blog/instructional_strategies
- Ukeh, B. O., Okeke, H. K., Okechukwu, O., Eziokwu, P. N., Onovo, N. E. & Orié, M. J. (2020). Effect of Prezi presentation software (PPS) on the achievement of students in computer studies. *International Journal of Integrated Research in Education*, 2(3), 51-57.
- Unugo, L. O. (2021). Effects of scaffolding teaching strategy on the academic achievement of students in social studies for value reorientation and national development. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 6(1), 92-100.

Whitman, M., & Mattord, H. J. (2018). *Principles of Information Security*. Cengage Learning.